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# Import necessary libraries
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
from keras.layers import Dense, LeakyReLU, Activation, Input, Dropout
from keras.models import Sequential, Model
from keras.optimizers import Adam
import keras.initializers as initializers
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.preprocessing import MinMaxScaler

# Load and preprocess your dataset (replace 'creditcard.csv' with your
dataset)
data = pd.read_csv("creditcard.csv")
X = data.iloc[:, 1:-1].values # Exclude the 'Time' and 'Class' columns
Y = data.iloc[:, -1].astype(float)

# Identify the minority class
minority_class = 1 # Change this value to match the minority class label

# Filter the dataset to include only the minority class samples
minority_samples = X[Y == minority_class]

# Define the desired number of rows for the oversampled minority class
desired_rows = 287000

# Calculate the number of times to repeat the minority class data
repeat_factor = desired_rows // len(minority_samples)

# Create the oversampled minority class by repeating the data
oversampled_minority = np.repeat(minority_samples, repeat_factor, axis=0)

# If necessary, add any remaining rows to meet the desired count
remaining_rows = desired_rows - len(oversampled_minority)
if remaining_rows > 0:
    oversampled_minority = np.vstack((oversampled_minority,
minority_samples[:remaining_rows]))

# Shuffle the oversampled minority class
np.random.shuffle(oversampled_minority)

# Define the Generator and Discriminator networks with reduced complexity
def build_generator(input_dim, optimizer):
    generator = Sequential()
    generator.add(Dense(64, input_dim=input_dim,
kernel_initializer=initializers.glorot_normal(seed=42)))
    generator.add(Activation('tanh'))
    generator.add(Dense(128))
    generator.add(Activation('tanh'))
    generator.add(Dense(256))
    generator.add(Activation('tanh'))
    generator.add(Dense(256))
    generator.add(Activation('tanh'))
    generator.add(Dense(512))
    generator.add(Activation('tanh'))
    generator.add(Dense(input_dim, activation='tanh'))
    generator.compile(loss='binary_crossentropy', optimizer=optimizer)
    return generator

def build_discriminator(input_dim, optimizer):
    discriminator = Sequential()

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        discriminator.add(Dense(128, input_dim=input_dim))
        discriminator.add(LeakyReLU(alpha=0.2))
        discriminator.add(Dropout(0.3))
        discriminator.add(Dense(1, activation='sigmoid'))
        discriminator.compile(loss='binary_crossentropy', optimizer=optimizer,
metrics=['accuracy'])
        return discriminator

# Combined model
def build_gan(generator, discriminator):
    discriminator.trainable = False # Freeze the discriminator during GAN
training
    gan_input = Input(shape=(input_dim,)) # Input for the generator
    generated_data = generator(gan_input)
    gan_output = discriminator(generated_data)
    gan = Model(gan_input, gan_output)
    return gan

# Hyperparameters
epochs = 50 # Reduce the number of epochs for faster training
batch_size = 128 # Use a larger batch size for faster training
learning_rate = 0.0002 # Experiment with different learning rates
input_dim = X.shape[1] # Dimensionality of the input data

# Build the networks
optimizer = Adam(learning_rate=learning_rate)
generator = build_generator(input_dim, optimizer)
discriminator = build_discriminator(input_dim, optimizer)
gan = build_gan(generator, discriminator)

# Compile the models
gan.compile(loss='binary_crossentropy', optimizer=optimizer)
discriminator.compile(loss='binary_crossentropy', optimizer=optimizer,
metrics=['accuracy'])

# Training loop (GAN training)
for epoch in range(epochs):
    for _ in range(len(oversampled_minority) // batch_size):
        # Sample random noise as input to the generator
        noise = np.random.normal(0, 1, size=[batch_size, input_dim])

        # Generate fake samples from the generator
        generated_samples = generator.predict(noise)

        # Sample real data from the oversampled minority class
        real_samples = oversampled_minority[np.random.randint(0,
len(oversampled_minority), size=batch_size)]

        # Create labels for the real and fake samples
        labels_real = np.ones((batch_size, 1))
        labels_fake = np.zeros((batch_size, 1))

        # Train the discriminator on real and fake samples separately
        discriminator_loss_real =
discriminator.train_on_batch(real_samples, labels_real)
        discriminator_loss_fake =
discriminator.train_on_batch(generated_samples, labels_fake)

        # Combine losses and train the generator
        gan_loss = 0.5 * np.add(discriminator_loss_fake,
discriminator_loss_real)

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generator_loss = gan.train_on_batch(noise, labels_real)

# Calculate and print the percentage of completion
completion_percentage = (epoch + 1) / epochs * 100

# Print training progress
print(f"Epoch {epoch + 1}/{epochs} [Discriminator loss:
{discriminator_loss_real}] [Generator loss: {generator_loss}]")
print(f"Completion: {completion_percentage:.2f}%")

# Generate augmented data for the minority class
num_generated_samples = len(oversampled_minority)
generated_data = generator.predict(np.random.normal(0, 1,
size=[num_generated_samples, input_dim]))

# Convert the generated data to a DataFrame
column_labels = list(data.columns)
generated_df = pd.DataFrame(data=generated_data, columns=column_labels[1:-
1]) # Exclude 'Time' and 'Class'

# Save the oversampled dataset to a CSV file
oversampled_data = pd.concat([data, generated_df], ignore_index=True)
oversampled_data.to_csv("oversampled_creditcard.csv", index=False)

# Now, you have the oversampled dataset with exactly 287,000 rows for the
minority class.

Classifier: SVM
Mean Accuracy: 1.00
Mean Precision: 1.00
Mean Recall: 1.00
Mean F1 Score: 1.00
Mean ROC AUC: 1.00
Std Accuracy: 0.00
Std Precision: 0.00
Std Recall: 0.00
Std F1 Score: 0.00
Std ROC AUC: 0.00
Execution Time: 93951.03 seconds
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Confusion Matrix for SVM

ROC Curve for SVM

Classifier: Logistic Regression
Mean Accuracy: 1.00
Mean Precision: 1.00
Mean Recall: 1.00
Mean F1 Score: 1.00
Mean ROC AUC: 1.00
Std Accuracy: 0.00
Std Precision: 0.00
Std Recall: 0.00
Std F1 Score: 0.00
Std ROC AUC: 0.00
Execution Time: 70.10 seconds

ROC Curve for Logistic Regression

Classifier: K-Nearest Neighbors
Mean Accuracy: 1.00
Mean Precision: 1.00
Mean Recall: 1.00
Mean F1 Score: 1.00
Mean ROC AUC: 1.00
Std Accuracy: 0.00
Std Precision: 0.00
Std Recall: 0.00
Std F1 Score: 0.00
Std ROC AUC: 0.00
Execution Time: 14090.50 seconds

ROC Curve for K-Nearest Neighbors

Classifier: Gaussian Naive Bayes
Mean Accuracy: 1.00
Mean Precision: 1.00
Mean Recall: 1.00
Mean F1 Score: 1.00
Mean ROC AUC: 1.00
Std Accuracy: 0.00
Std Precision: 0.00
Std Recall: 0.00
Std F1 Score: 0.00
Std ROC AUC: 0.00
Execution Time: 6.39 seconds

ROC Curve for Gaussian Naive Bayes

Classifier: Random Forest
Mean Accuracy: 1.00
Mean Precision: 1.00
Mean Recall: 1.00
Mean F1 Score: 1.00
Mean ROC AUC: 1.00
Std Accuracy: 0.00
Std Precision: 0.00
Std Recall: 0.00
Std F1 Score: 0.00
Std ROC AUC: 0.00
Execution Time: 3019.05 seconds

ROC Curve for Random Forest